

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF MOBILE LEARNING. MOBILE APP LANGUAGE TRAINING AND TEACHING.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15575307>

Abstract: The article is devoted to the role and pedagogical aspects of mobile learning, об innovative technologies of the XXI century in teaching the Russian language. It examines the importance of modern technologies for increasing students' interest in learning a language, as well as effective methods of using these technologies in the educational process.

Keywords: mobile learning, methodology, exercise, multimedia.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена о роли и педагогических аспектах мобильного обучения, об инновационных технологий XXI века в обучении русскому языку. В ней рассматривается важность современных технологий для повышения интереса обучающихся к изучению языка, а также эффективные методы использования этих технологий в учебном процессе.

Ключевые слова: мобильное обучение, методика, упражнение, мультимедиа.

Modern society cannot be imagined without the widespread use of mobile media and various data transmission systems, which have become widespread and publicly available. Currently, mobile devices are radically transforming our lives. With their help, new forms of art, changes in the language, new professions are emerging, and a new direction in education is developing - training using mobile technologies.

Learning with mobile technologies (m-learning) opens up new opportunities for both students and teachers. Thanks to the development of mobile devices such as smartphones, tablets, and other portable devices, learning becomes more flexible, accessible, and efficient. The advantages of this format are as follows:

1. Flexibility and accessibility. Students can access study materials anytime and anywhere with an internet connection. This allows them to combine their studies with everyday activities and plan their time more effectively. For

teachers, this means the ability to submit assignments and evaluate results, regardless of geographical location.

2. Interactivity and diversity. Mobile devices support a variety of content formats: text documents, audio files, video materials, interactive tests and simulations. This helps to diversify the learning process, making it more fun and contributing to better assimilation of information.

3. Support for different learning styles. Educational materials can be presented in various formats, which allows you to take into account the individual characteristics of students, their preferences and ways of perceiving information. For example, students can choose audio or video materials to study, which is especially useful when studying foreign languages, including Russian.

4. Develop independent learning skills. Students get the opportunity to plan and organize their own learning process, развивая thus developing time management and self-discipline skills. Teachers can provide guidance and guidance to students, but students can do most of the work themselves, which contributes to the development of their autonomy.

5. Feedback and evaluation. Teachers can quickly provide feedback via mobile platforms, allowing students to quickly correct their mistakes and improve their skills. It also helps to maintain a high level of motivation, as students see their progress and can immediately work to improve.

Mobile learning (m-learning) in a broad sense is the use of mobile devices, such as mobile phones, smartphones, tablets, laptops and other portable gadgets, to organize the learning process, regardless of the place and time. This training format is closely related to e-learning, but the main difference is the use of mobile devices. There is an opinion in scientific circles that electronic technologies have a wider potential than mobile ones. However, given the rapid development of mobile technologies, limitations such as device speed, battery life, and screen size are considered temporary difficulties.

The researchers note that mobile learning, as a type of e-learning, fully corresponds to the concept of flexible education, which gives students the freedom to choose the place, time and method of learning. The diagram illustrates the relationship between mobile, e-learning, and flexible learning.

A special feature of mobile learning is its ability to provide instant access to educational materials anywhere and at a convenient time for the student. Using mobile technologies, students can effectively collaborate on group projects and interact with the teacher outside of school hours.

Mobile devices contribute to the introduction of an individualized approach to learning, allowing students to choose the most appropriate style of information perception: visual (using photos, images, videos, and graphs), auditory (with an emphasis on audio files and music), logical (based on logical reasoning and systematization), and others. The selection of educational materials also takes place in accordance with the interests and needs of students. As a rule, many students store collections of links, bookmarks, reference books and mobile applications on their mobile devices for learning purposes, based on their preferences.

This creates a personalized and professionally oriented educational space for each student. The learning process becomes timely, sufficient, and individually oriented ("just-in-time, just enough, and just-for-me").

Mobile learning opens up countless opportunities for the methodology of teaching foreign languages. If until the 1990s, insufficient language proficiency was often associated with a lack of immersion in the natural language environment, then with the development of information technologies, this problem was successfully solved through virtual communication. Mobile technologies have become one of the most accessible and widely used tools for accessing the virtual language environment.

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